

An evaluation of buffer- and rate-based HTTP adaptive streaming strategies

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Abstract—Video streaming has become an indispensable technology in people’s lives. However, the variability and instability of network conditions poses one of the biggest challenges to video streaming. In this paper, we study HTTP Adaptive Streaming (HAS), a technology that relieves these issues by adapting the video reproduction to the current network conditions. More specifically, we classify HAS strategies and evaluate buffer-based and rate-based solutions both independently and in combination with each other. Our simulations demonstrate that buffer-based policies offer better results in terms of Quality of Experience (QoE) metrics such as quality layer selection and frequency of quality switches, while rate-based policies lead to less video stalling.

Keywords—HTTP Adaptive Streaming, Quality of Experience, video streaming, MPEG-DASH, buffer policy, rate policy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade there has been an unprecedented increase in the number of mobile devices. Accompanied by the improvement of their computing power, this change brought a notable turn to the provisioned services. New services have appeared, while video streaming is expected to grow to more than 80 percent of all consumer Internet traffic by 2020 [1]. At the same time, end users, aware of the rapidly evolving technology, set new standards for providers, as they expect high-quality, smooth uninterrupted video experience.

The fact that mobile devices are a vital part of our everyday lives is posing several problems for providers since video traffic is growing at an immense rate stretching networks to their limits. Correspondingly, there is a vast increase in the number of available video hosting companies trying to meet consumer demands and offer them a pleasant experience. The most significant problems that providers face are related to network condition issues such as packet loss, insufficient bandwidth, delay, and jitter, which can lead to video stalling, the main reason a user is disappointed by a video streaming service [2]. As Quality of Experience (QoE) is the ultimate goal of providers, the services must adapt in order to offer the best possible result diminishing any undesirable effects.

Traditional HTTP video streaming (video on demand - VoD) has been the dominant server-based technique for progressive video streaming until recently. However, in the attempt to tackle the ever-increasing bandwidth limitations, HTTP video streaming is gradually being replaced by the client-based technique known as HTTP Adaptive Streaming (HAS), adopted by YouTube as well. Because HAS operates from a

client standpoint, it is effectively allowing greater flexibility to client-server communication, which leads to more promising ways of dealing with these challenges and increasing end user QoE.

II. OVERVIEW OF HTTP ADAPTIVE STREAMING

Generally, a HAS system needs to take specific actions on the server and client side. On the server side, the main concern is the preparation of the content, i.e., selection of available representations, and optimal encoding. This also includes proper selection of system parameters, such as the length of an encoded segment. Among the server-side actions is also the selection of compression algorithms for audiovisual content (in cases where it is not fixed by the system specification).

On the client side, the most important decisions are which segments to download, when to start with the download, and how to manage the receiver video buffer. The adaptation algorithm (decision engine) should select the appropriate representations that maximize QoE. This is usually a tradeoff between diminishing stalling probability and requesting high bit rate. In a typical HAS streaming session, at first, the client makes a request to the server via HTTP in order to obtain information about the different audio and video representations available. This information is contained in an index file. The name of this file may differ for each HAS implementation, for example, in MPEG-DASH the index file is called Media Presentation Description (MPD), while other technologies use the terms manifest or playlist. The sole purpose of this file is to provide a list of representations available to the client and a way to manage HTTP requests for every representation that is chosen.

The difficulty in a HAS implementation falls in its ability to switch among different representations at fixed, frequent time instants during the playback. To achieve this, a decision engine/algorithm is used to perform the right adaptations. The adaptation engine in the client, also called HAS strategy, decides which of the media segments should be downloaded by considering their availability, the network conditions (like estimated throughput), and the playout conditions (like playout buffer fill level). In order for smooth switching among different representations to be achieved, it is required that the segments corresponding to different representations are perfectly time aligned [3]. Then the user splices the segments together and begins playback. This method is shown to greatly reduce stalling in many environments.

In order for a HAS implementation to be effective, some requirements need to be fulfilled regarding the adaptation rate. First, a metric must be used in the adaptation strategy to check whether the bitrate of a specific representation matches the available end-to-end bandwidth. This metric is expected to recognize throughput changes due to network bandwidth variations. To achieve efficient rate adaptation, the metric should identify any mismatch between the representation bitrate and the available end-to-end bandwidth very quickly. Second, the HAS strategy has to manage the client buffer in order to prevent buffer underflows and overflows. Third, the strategy should be equipped with good convergence property and prevent hopping between neighbor media representations. Last, the segment duration needs to be properly adjusted so that the HTTP overhead is as minimum as possible, thus reducing the delay introduced by HTTP request processing and transmission and maximizing the adaptation speed [4]. A representation of the HAS logic is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: HAS logic in a mobile network

III. CLASSIFICATION OF HAS STRATEGIES

A plethora of HAS strategies has recently appeared. Below, we categorize these strategies into commercial solutions, standardized approaches and research proposals.

A. Commercial implementations

After the first launch of a HAS solution by Move Networks in 2007, HAS was implemented by three large scale companies at the same time. These companies were Microsoft, Apple and Adobe Systems. Although their solutions may be different, they are based on similar principles.

a) Microsoft Silverlight Smooth Streaming (MSS)

MSS [5] was introduced by Microsoft Corporation in 2008. This adaptive streaming method combines CPU utilization, playback window resolution and constant bandwidth detection at the client in order to deliver high quality content with no delay. The word “smooth” in its name shows that this adaptation strategy focuses on switching between media segments as best as possible while constantly monitoring network conditions. The adaptive streaming technology is implemented through the Silverlight client, a free web-browser plug-in. The supported video codecs are VC-1 advanced and H.264 (Baseline, Main and High). The media container is audio codec agnostic in theory but only has two supported audio types: WMA and AAC. The typical media segment length is 2 seconds.

b) Apple HTTP Live Streaming (HLS)

HLS [6] was introduced by Apple Inc. in 2009. This streaming technique supports baseline H.264 video codecs and three

audio types, MP3, HE-AAC and AAC-LC. The typical media segment length is 10 seconds. Unlike the previously mentioned MSS which uses MPEG-4 part-12/Fragmented MP4 container media format, HLS uses MPEG-2 Transport Stream (MPEG-2 TS) which approximately adds a 24% overhead to video and audio data. It is specifically made to be used along iOS devices only, such as iPhones, OSX desktops and iPads. HLS was especially designed for mobile environments with the ability to request more than one segment with each HTTP 1.1 GET request which leads to eliminating a significant amount of RTTs.

c) HTTP Dynamic Streaming (HDS)

HDS [7] was introduced by Adobe Systems Inc. in 2010. HDS supports H.264 video codecs and MP3 or AAC audio types. The typical segment length is 4 seconds. The file format used for media content delivery complies with the MPEG-4 part 12 and is called F4V (its origin is the Adobe FLV format) file format. So, there will be some similarities between HDS and MSS. Like in MSS, a media stream either VoD or live stream is broken down to smaller pieces called fragments. In HDS, fragments are the smallest units of media that can be addressed and delivered. Fragments could contain video or audio data representing some seconds of the content (e.g. 3-4s) and are independently decodable. One or more fragments can be grouped to form a larger contiguous unit called segment. The purpose of forming segments is to improve storage by reducing the number of files to be managed by the file system and simultaneously increase cache efficiency since caching proxies can fetch whole segments even though the requests they serve ask for individual fragments.

B. Standards: MPEG-DASH

Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) was issued by Moving Pictures Experts Group (MPEG) in 2012. This standard was created to unite all the existing solutions (MSS, HLS, HDS and others) as much as possible. DASH is codec agnostic which means that it defines segment container formats for MPEG-2 TS and ISO Base Media File Format. There is also no segment length specified, so the length picking has to be done by the ones making the implementations. The only things that DASH defines are the segment formats and the Multimedia Presentation Description (MPD). So, the delivery of the MPD and the media-encoding formats containing the segments, as well as the client behavior for fetching, adaptation heuristics, and playing content, are outside of MPEG DASH’s scope [8].

C. Research proposals

A plethora of HAS mechanisms have emerged in the research literature as well. Most common are bandwidth-based approaches, where segment selection decisions adapt to the network conditions, as these are perceived by the end users through their experience with previously downloaded segments. Variations of these approaches attempt to additionally mitigate the frequency and altitude of quality level switches (i.e. to stay robust against network bandwidth fluctuations) [9]. Prediction-based approaches take more informed decisions using intelligence about the future network

conditions that a user is going to face, available either from historical data about the bandwidth in combination with geo-location information [10], or, by network link or load prediction techniques (e.g. Holt-Winters, etc.) [11]. Current literature also contains buffer-based strategies, which measure the user's buffer filling level as a stalling-safety policy often combined with rate-based knowledge, whereas capability-based strategies account for device limitations, such as CPU utilization and battery life [12], in an effort to take more personalized decisions.

In this paper, we focus on buffer based and rate based strategies, as well as their combinations. In this context, the evaluated strategies are described as follows:

1) Strategy 1 (S1) – Buffer based

This strategy uses a threshold-based buffer based algorithm. This algorithm checks the buffer level before every segment download and if the buffer is above a certain threshold B_{suff} (it is sufficiently full), the higher available quality of the next segment (if one exists) is selected. If the buffer is below another threshold B_{dep} (is near depletion), the lower quality of the next segment (if one exists) is selected for download. In any other case, the quality requested is the same as the previous segment.

2) Strategy 2 (S2) – Rate based

This strategy makes an estimation of the bandwidth based on the segment download rate of the last N segments and selects the best representation (quality) of the next segment that fits this estimation.

3) Strategy 3 (S3) – Buffer based with rate logic

This strategy is based on [9]. Three buffer thresholds B_{dep} (depletion threshold), B_{st} (stable threshold) and B_{tar} (target threshold) are used. Before the download of every segment, S3 checks the current buffer level and makes an estimation of the bandwidth. Then the following decisions are made:

- If the current buffer level is between B_{st} and B_{tar} , the quality selected is the same as for the previous segment.
- If the current buffer level is equal or higher than B_{tar} , S3 checks if there is a higher quality that fits the bandwidth estimation and if one exists, it selects the higher quality.
- If the current buffer level is between B_{dep} and B_{st} , S3 checks if the highest quality available fits the estimated bandwidth and if it does, it keeps the previous quality. Otherwise, the quality selected is the next lower than the previous quality.
- If the current buffer level is below B_{dep} , then S3 selects the lowest possible quality in order to avoid buffer depletion.

This strategy is more conservative because quality changes only occur when the conditions (buffer level and bandwidth estimation) are either too good or too bad.

4) Strategy 4 (S4) – Buffer based or rate based

The idea behind this strategy is the combination of S1 and S2, namely it uses the buffer based and the rate based algorithm and chooses the maximum result from those two.

In the next section, we compare and evaluate these HAS strategies.

IV. EVALUATION STUDY

A. Evaluation environment

The evaluation was performed in a MATLAB based simulation environment. The buffer of the client is a queuing model where the downloaded segments are considered as arrivals, and the played segments as departures. As far as the estimation of the download rate is concerned, we used a sliding window approach. The network traffic was simulated using real traces recorded from a real vehicular mobility scenario, as in [13]. We run the simulation for all the network traces using various bandwidth profiles to simulate different network congestion levels. Those profiles are determined by a variable called bw_factor (bandwidth factor). When this factor has a low value, more congestion is present in the network and vice versa. Moreover, we have implemented a video streaming session where the client is moving while streaming video. The initial behavior of the client is to fill the buffer up to the playout threshold causing initial delay. After the buffer is sufficiently full, video playback begins. Each segment is downloaded using the HAS strategy/algorithm under consideration. Parameters considered for the simulation are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Segment duration	2 sec
Number of video segments	350
Available representations (layers) per segment	2
Quality of the first segment	1
Buffer playout threshold	8 segments
Buffer depletion threshold B_{dep} for S1, S3, S4	10 segments
Buffer maximum size	∞
Bandwidth factor	0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1
Network traces	30 different

In order to perform the comparison and evaluation of the four HAS strategies, we calculated the following averaged values: percentage of time on each quality layer, number of quality switches, QoE scores, and number of stalling events.

B. Study of individual HAS strategies

We first ran the simulation for a fixed value of $bw_factor = 0.4$ (high network congestion) with different values for the buffer thresholds and for the segment number used for the bandwidth estimation N (i.e. N is the size of the sliding window used for rate estimation), to test how the behavior of each strategy changes. Regarding the buffer thresholds, we changed the values of B_{suff} (used by S1 and S4), B_{tar} and B_{st} (used by S3). The depletion thresholds have the same value $B_{dep} = 10$.

In Figure 2a we present the average percentage of quality layer selection over the values of the B_{suff} threshold for S1. We can see that S1 performs better for $B_{suff} = 40$ by requesting 39% of the segments with high quality and 61% of the segments with low quality. In Figure 2b we also observe that S1 causes the least number of quality switches for $B_{suff} = 50$. As the value of the B_{suff} threshold increases, the number of quality switches decreases, because it takes more segments

to fill the buffer to a sufficient level for higher values of the threshold, thus more segments are downloaded with low quality and less switches are caused. We also calculated the average QoE scores over the B_{suff} value, which are however similar in the range of 2.52 to 2.53. The average number of stalling events is shown in Figure 2c, where we can see that S1 presents almost no stalling events for $B_{suff} = 40$ and $B_{suff} = 50$. This happens because as the value of B_{suff} increases, more segments are downloaded with low quality until the value of the threshold is reached and so the buffer contains enough segments so that buffer depletion is avoided.

For S2, we present the layer selection over the number of past segments N used for the bandwidth estimation. The results are shown in Figure 3a, where we can see that S2 selects high quality for 8.5% of the segments and low quality for the rest 91.5% when $N = 10$, while for the other values of N , S2 selects high quality for about 7% of the segments. So, for $N = 10$, S2 presents the best results. This means that S2 gives better results when less segments are considered to make the bandwidth estimation, namely when the past window is smaller and contains, presumably, more valid estimations. As far as the quality switches that S2 causes over the N values is concerned, the results are shown in Figure 3b. From this figure, we can see that S2 causes the least number of quality switches for $N = 20$. QoE scores are also similar, while S2 presents no stalling events for all N values that were tested.

In Figure 4a we present the layer selection over the values of B_{tar} and B_{st} thresholds for S3. S3 selects higher quality for the segments when $B_{tar} = 40$ and $B_{st} = 20$. The percentage of the segments with high quality is 37% and with low quality 63%. In Figure 4b we present the average number of quality switches, where we can see that for $B_{tar} = 40$ and $B_{st} = 20$, S3 causes the least switches, because for these values of the thresholds (under high network congestion), the buffer of S3 fills at a more stable rate, thus not causing as many switches as for the other values. The results for the average QoE scores are also similar, while S3 causes no stalling events for all the values of thresholds we tested.

Regarding S4, we set the parameter $N = 10$ so that we can get the best performance (based on the results for S2) from the rate logic. We tested the behavior of S4 for different values of the B_{suff} threshold. In Figure 5a we can see that S4 performs better when $B_{suff} = 50$. In this case, S4 selects 44% of the segments with high quality and 56% of the segments with low quality. What is interesting is that although S4 uses the buffer logic of S1, the combination of rate and buffer logic present better results for $B_{suff} = 50$ (instead of $B_{suff} = 40$). Next, in Figure 5b, we can see that S4 causes the least number of quality switches for $B_{suff} = 50$. Furthermore, the number of quality switches keeps decreasing for higher values of B_{suff} because S4 has the same buffer logic with S1, but the number of switches caused for each value of the threshold is higher than in the case of S1. QoE scores are similar, while S4 presents no stalling events for $B_{suff} = 30$ and very few stalling events for the rest of the values of the threshold (Figure 5c). What is also interesting is that although S4 uses

the same rate logic with S2, which completely avoids stalling, stalling events occur. This happens because most of the segment quality decisions are made by the buffer logic instead of the rate logic. Also, for high values of B_{suff} more stalling events occur.

C. Comparative study of HAS strategies

In this section, we compare all four strategies. We measured the percentage of time that each strategy spends on each layer against the values of the bw_factor . We found that for the lowest value of bw_factor S1, S3 and S4 spend about 90% of their time on the lowest quality layer while S2 spends almost 100%. This is expected because the congestion of the network is high. As congestion decreases, we saw that all strategies cause more time on the high-quality layer (layer 2). An interesting observation is that for an average congestion level ($bw_factor = 0.5$), the strategies S1, S3 and S4 that take into consideration the buffer level cause a higher percentage of time spent on the high layer (around 50%), while S2 spends less than 30%.

We also measured the average number of quality switches each strategy causes during varying network congestion as well as the impact on QoE. The results of these two simulations are shown in Figures 6a and 6b, respectively. As QoE model, we used the equation $QoE = 0.003e^{0.064t} + 2.498$ where t is the percentage of time spent on the highest quality layer [13]. Regarding the number of quality switches each strategy causes, we can clearly see that the conservative S3 makes the least number of switches for all test cases, followed by S1, S4 and S2. Furthermore, as congestion in the network decreases, S1, S3 and S4 cause fewer quality switches at a stable rate, in contrast to S2 that starts decreasing the number of switches only when very low congestion is present ($bw_factor \geq 0.8$). The maximum number of switches for S1, S3 and S4 occurs when $bw_factor = 0.4$ and for S2 when $bw_factor = 0.8$. By looking now at Figure 6b and considering that the QoE model is based on the time spent on the high-quality layer, we can see that S4 has the advantage, followed by S1, S3 and S2. This figure indicates that the combination of buffer and rate criteria used in S4 perform better than other strategies regarding QoE, which is expected, since the highest layer proposed by either approach is selected. Regarding the average number of stalling events that occur for each strategy depending on the values of the bw_factor , the results are shown in Figure 6c. We see that for $bw_factor \geq 0.6$ no strategy presents any stalling event. Furthermore, S2 presents no stalling events for every case we tested. S3 presents a very few number of stalling events for high network congestion while S1 and S4 present the highest number of stalling events overall. From this figure, we concluded that the rate logic of S2 presents better results than any other strategy when it comes to stalling.

D. Evaluation conclusion

Strategy 1 (S1) selects higher quality segments at a stable rate as the network congestion decreases. Also, S1 causes a small number of switches. However, for high network congestion it can easily lead to stalling.

Strategy 2 (S2) selects mostly low quality segments and because of that it leads to the lowest QoE scores. It also causes much more switches compared to the other three strategies.

On the other hand, the rate logic of S2 can completely avoid stalling events and thus, offer a smooth playback of the video to the end user.

Figure 2. a) Percentage of quality layer selection, b) Number of quality switches, c) Average number of stalling events - over B_{suff} threshold for S1

Figure 3. a) Percentage of quality layer selection, b) Number of quality switches - over the bandwidth estimation number N for S2

Figure 4. a) Percentage of quality layer selection, b) Number of quality switches - over B_{tar} and B_{st} thresholds for S3

Figure 5. a) Percentage of quality layer selection, b) Number of quality switches, c) Average number of stalling events - over B_{suff} threshold for S4

Figure 6. a) Number of quality switches, b) QoE scores, c) Number of stalling events

Strategy 3 (S3) has a similar behavior to S1 regarding the quality level selected. It causes the least number of quality switches compared to the other strategies and in high network congestion, it can handle stalling very well.

Strategy 4 (S4) gives the best QoE scores, which means that it selects higher quality for more segments than the other strategies, thus, offering a high-quality video playback. It also causes more switches than S1 and S3, because it contains the rate logic of S2. The problem for S4 is that it can easily lead to stalling when high network congestion occurs.

We also came to some conclusions about buffer logic versus rate logic. We noticed that the strategies which involve buffer logic (S1, S3 and S4) make less switches and offer higher quality of video than rate logic strategies (S2). On the contrary, rate logic can handle stalling better. Finally, the strategy that uses a combination of buffer and rate logic offers better quality of video than the pure buffer logic and the pure rate logic strategies.

V. FUTURE WORK

HAS solutions have shown great potential in media delivery, as witnessed by their increasingly widespread deployments. However, there are several technical challenges that need to be addressed before they can approach the service quality that users expect, such as high bitrate, smooth playback of high definition video, 3D video and live streaming.

Most of the challenges have to do with the limited amount of bandwidth availability. Nowadays, HAS decisions are taken based on each user's short-sighted perception of the available network bandwidth, which results in a sub-optimal, and potentially greedy or unstable behavior. Schemes where the user's perception can be improved to better reflect the actual network state have, therefore, to be further investigated. In this case, trade-offs between more accurate global knowledge of the system and complexity issues have to be considered. Also, there is a need for better coordination of the cross-layer information (network and application layer). So, how to combine the underlying network information with the application layer to improve the user's QoE is an interesting future research direction. Moreover, since there are many

HAS solutions proposed, it is essential to develop instrumentation tools with friendly user interface to assess their effectiveness and performance and provide adequate information for diagnosis and fault isolation.

We showed that current HAS solutions mainly decide on adaptation based on bandwidth measurements and buffer levels. However, the resulting QoE, which is affected by adaptation, is not well defined. Hence, there is a need for the creation of a standardized QoE model for HAS applications. Future HAS solutions should be QoE-driven, context aware, and collaborative, such that especially end users but also other interested parties benefit from improved adaptation decisions and improved quality of video streaming services.

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REFERENCES

- [1] White paper: Cisco VNI Forecast and Methodology, 2015-2020.
- [2] T. Hoßfeld, et al., "Initial delay vs. interruptions: Between the devil and the deep blue sea," in IEEE QoMEX, 2012, pp. 1-6.
- [3] M. Seufert, et al., "A survey on Quality of Experience of HTTP adaptive streaming," IEEE Comm. Surveys & Tutorials, pp. 469-486, 2015.
- [4] C. Liu, et al., "Rate adaptation for adaptive HTTP streaming," in ACM MMSys. 2011, pp. 169-174.
- [5] Microsoft Smooth Streaming Protocol. [MS-SSTR], 2016, online: <https://msdn.microsoft.com/en-us/library/ff469518.aspx>.
- [6] Apple Inc., HTTP Live Streaming, IETF draft, 2016, online: <https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-pantos-http-live-streaming-20>.
- [7] Adobe Systems, "HTTP dynamic streaming specification," 2013, online: <http://www.wimages.adobe.com/content/dam/Adobe/en/devnet/hds/pdfs/adobe-hdsspecification.pdf>.
- [8] I. Sodagar, "The MPEG-DASH standard for multimedia streaming over the Internet," IEEE Multimed., vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 62-67, 2011.
- [9] H. T. Le, et al., "A novel adaptation method for HTTP streaming of VBR videos over mobile networks," Mob. Inf. Syst., pp. 1-11, 2016.
- [10] J. Hao, et al., "GTube: Geo-predictive video streaming over HTTP in mobile environments," in ACM MMSys, 2014, pp. 259-270.
- [11] Y. Liu and J. Y. B. Lee, "On adaptive video streaming with predictable streaming performance," in IEEE GLOBECOM, 2014, pp. 1164-1169.
- [12] S. Petrangeli, et al., "Energy-aware quality adaptation for mobile video streaming," in IEEE CNSM, 2016, pp. 253-257.
- [13] T. Hoßfeld, et al., "Identifying QoE optimal adaptation of HTTP adaptive streaming based on subjective studies," Computer Networks, vol. 81, pp. 320-332, 2015.